

Problems and Solutions in Female Education

A Historical View

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ABSTRACT

Dr. Sarvepalli Radha Krishnan the first Vice-President and the second President of India quoting that Manu believed “Where women are honoured there the Gods are pleased, where they are not honoured all work becomes fruitless “. Women as human beings have as much right as men have and the honour they expect in society depends on the degree of their education. The education of women is an inevitable part of development of any country. For the betterment of women education many steps are being taken for example for improving and expanding their facilities in educational institutions. Due to lack of funds all these steps are in slow pace. The present scenario in the society for girls as well as women education has been facing many problems such as illiterate parents; do not know the value of education, lack of schools and colleges in their vicinity, lack of toilets in schools, child marriages, social traditions and customs. These barriers should be removed by government and family members at different level. Education is the only weapon which has the power to change the world. So, let's support for Women education, empower women as well as India.

Keywords : Women , Education , Barriers , Illiterate , Family.

Introduction

The women education in India is one of the problems which attract our attention immediately. In our country, due to conservative traditionalism and thinking, women's status has been considered to be lower than that of men and treated the women as Kitchen Rabbit. During the later Vedic period the Aryans had sealed the destiny of women. Her presence was curtailed culturally, socially and denying them the right to learn the Vedas, thus half of the population was deprived or kept away from the Education was one of the most fundamental human rights of women. They were considered as the bonded slave to men and do not have economic independence. Even today, women have to fight for their equal rights and status in the society. They sought the help and completely relied on men until the end of their life. Illiteracy and ignorance is more prevalent in women folk than in men and this evil is uncontrolled especially in lower and backward communities in rural areas.

Objectives :

- To Study the Women Education Through the Ages In India
- To Study the Current Policies of Women Education in India
- In analyse the Problems of Women Education in India
- To given Some Important Suggestions and Recommendations to Improve Female Literacy Rate in India

Methodology of the Study

The present study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on Primary and secondary sources of data. The sample covers the period from 2021 census data. The main source of data to various Census Surveys of India and online data base of Indian census Statistics, Government Orders, Reports of the Government, Journals, Articles etc.

Women Education Through the Ages in India

In any community, the education of women is a more complex task than the education of men. On this subject, a vast variety of views have been expounded. Man's ego has generally adopted a biased view of the education of women. The Vedic period

consistently believed that despite the differences in physiology, woman is in no way intellectually inferior to man. She possesses excellent memory, intelligence, and other mental powers, and hence she has the capacity to obtain any kind of education.

A woman's fulfilment lies in womanhood and the latter's in motherhood. It is because of this that the nature of feminine education differs from that of masculine education. She should be skilled in household duties. Consequently, girls were educated at home, despite which the names of such women as Vishwavara, Jboha, Apalla, Ghosha, Romsa, Lopamudra, Saraswati and others are mentioned in ancient texts, as examples of women who composed commentaries on the Vedas. This was the earlier condition of education of women in Vedic period. Afterwards the women education was neglected.¹

In the Buddhist period, women occupied a position inferior to men. Initially, they were prohibited from joining a Sangha or congregation. Later on, they were granted admission to such congregations and it was then that feminine education progressed. Dr. Altekar points out that the permission for women to enter congregations gave great encouragement to feminine education, particularly to the education of women belonging to the noble and trading classes.

There is considerable evidence to prove that feminine education prevailed during this period. Separate monasteries were established for women. Among the women who attained fame were Sheel Bhattarika, Vijayanka, Prabhudevi etc. A lady named Sanghmitra went to Ceylon to propagate the Buddhist faith.²

During the Muslim period, education developed very slowly that no notable characteristic of it ever emerged. Minor rulers had educational institutions established for the satisfaction of their interests. However, the following features can be noted in them Encouragement by the State, Arabic and Persian, Religious influence, Materialism, Development of History. The education of women was completely neglected during this period. Special provisions were however made for ladies belonging to the royal families. Besides, since a sense of insecurity prevailed almost everywhere, no attention was paid to the education of women.³

English education in India has its foundation in the 18th century. The missionaries came to India with the East India Company and various measures were adopted to

educate the local population. The missionary activities also included conversion to Christianity and as such the Indian population was weary of the education given by them. In 1773 Warren Hastings established the foundation of British Education.⁴ The controversy was generated because of the education being Western in its content and delivery. The 'purdah' system, the system of child marriage and the general indifference of parents to the education of their daughters acted as a check to the progress of female education.

The Western education was highly responsible for many social and religious reforms in the Indian Country equally protected or accepted. However, with the introduction of western education many Indians who had the access to western ideologies persistently urged the British Indian Government to enact laws in protection of women. Consequently the British Government passed social enactments. As a result the modern women got education, property and other rights on par with men in India.⁵

After independence, India has been taking active steps towards women's education and their empowerment. In our Constitutions take a progressive step through the 86th Constitutional Amendment Act in 2002, this historical remark is very important especially for development of women education.⁶ According to this act, elementary education is a fundamental right for children between the age of 6 and 14. The government has undertaken to provide the education free of cost and make it compulsory for those in that age group.⁷ This project is more broadly conceived as Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) . The SSA has come up with many scheme for inclusive as well as exclusive growth of Indian education as a whole, including scheme to help foster the growth of women education.⁸ The major schemes are following here.

Mahila Samakhya Programme

This Programme was launched in 1988 in pursuance of the goals of the New Education policy (1986) and the Programme of Action as a concrete programme for the education in rural areas, particularly of women from socially and economically marginalised groups. The program aimed at the development of women and removing gender – based discrimination from the country. It is being implemented in more than 15,800 villages spread over 63 districts of nine States viz,⁹ Andhra Pradesh ,Assam,

Bihar, Gujarat, Jharkhand ,Karnataka, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh and Uttaranchat. The Mahila Samakhya Scheme will expand to cover two new States of Madhya Pradesh and Chattisgarh During 2006 – 2007.¹⁰

National Perspective Plan for Women's Education

Formulated some important specific objectives for women education so that women may also participate in the area of social, cultural, economic, political and education. These important objectives to be obtained by 2000 A.D.,¹¹ in regard to women's education are : Elimination of illiteracy, universalization of elementary education and minimization of the dropout rate in the age group 6-14 years and stagnation to negligible proportions; Substantial vocationalization and diversification of secondary education so as to provide a wide scope for employment and economic independence of women ; Making education an effective means for women's equality by (a) Addressing ourselves to the constraint that prevent women from participating in the educational process, (b) Eliminating the existing bias in the system, (c) making necessary intervention in the content and processes of education to inculcate positive and egalitarian attitudes, and (d) Ensuring that teachers' perceive this as one of their essential roles. Awareness needs to be generated among the masses regarding the necessity of educating girls so as to prepare them to effectively contribute the socio- economic development of the country, to strengthen their role in society and to realize their own capacities. The media and various forms of communication have to be geared to this end.

National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level (NPEGEL)

The National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level (NPEGEL) is a programme of Government of India, to reach the "Hardest to Reach" girls, especially those who were not in school. Launched in July 2003, it is an important component of SSA, which provides additional support for enhancing girl's education. The programme provides for development of a "Model School" in every cluster with more intense community mobilization and supervision of girls enrolment in schools.¹² Gender sensitisation of teachers, development of gender sensitive learning materials and provision of need-based incentives like escorts, stationery, workbooks and uniforms are some of the endeavours under the programme, The scheme is implemented exclusively

for enrolling, retaining and empowering girls studying in regular Primary education by establishing Model Cluster Schools to provide academic standard to all the other schools in the cluster.

Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya Scheme (KGBV)

With concerted efforts, Government of Tamilnadu has been able to bridge the gap between the gender and social category by providing access, empowering them through various interventions such as National Programme for Girls at Elementary Level launched in July 2003, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya programme launched in the year 2004-2005, Special programmes for girls implemented in 2008-09.¹³ Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya programme (KGBV) is a special intervention to set up residential schools in the educationally backward blocks with free boarding facilities and ensuring access to girls especially at upper primary level for whom social, cultural taboos and economic conditions hindered their educational improvement. Quality education is being imparted in these schools. The scheme of the KGBV ran as a separate scheme in harmony with the SSA, NPEGEL and Mahila Samkhyā (MS) for the first 2 years but on and from 1st April, 2007, KGBV merged with the SSA programme as a separate component.¹⁴

Girls' Hostels

The Government of India has launched a new centrally sponsored scheme called Scheme for "Construction and running of Girls Hostels for students of Secondary and Higher Secondary Schools". The main objective of the scheme was enrolment and retention of girls in High Schools and Higher Secondary Schools. This scheme was launched in 2008-09 and is being implemented from 2009-10 to set up girl's hostel with a capacity of 100 beds in each of the 3479 educationally backward blocks (EBBS) in the country.¹⁵

This scheme has replaced the earlier NGO driven Scheme for construction and running of Girls' Hostels for Students of Secondary and Higher Secondary Schools, where assistance was provided to voluntary organisations for running Girls' Hostels. The expenditure of the project will be shared between the Central and State Governments in the ratio of 90:10. The beneficiaries will be girls of the age group of 14 to 18 studying in Standards IX to XII. Each hostel will have a capacity to accommodate 100 girls.¹⁶ This

Scheme will be implemented in convergence with the "Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidhyalaya" (KGBV) scheme of the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan programme.

National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education (NSIGSE)

To encourage SC/ST girl students Studying in Standard VIII, the National scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education was launched during 2008-09. Under this scheme the Sc/ST girl students who a completed Standard VIII and studying in Standard IX but not completed 16 years of age are eligible to get Rs.3,000/- as incentive.¹⁷

The amount of Rs.3,000/- will be deposited in students' name in Nationalized Banks. Girls, who pass VIII standard examination from Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidhyalayas (irrespective of whether they belong to Scheduled Castes or Tribes) and enrol for class IX in State/UT Government and should be unmarried and below 16 years of age (as on 31st March) are eligible for the benefit under the scheme.

Saakshar Bharat (Karkum Bharatham)

The Prime Minister of India launched Saakshar Bharat, a centrally sponsored scheme of Department of School Education and Literacy (DSEL), Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India (GOI) on the International Literacy Day, 8th September, 2009.

It aimed at promoting and strengthening Adult Education, especially for women. This programme was being implemented by National Literacy Mission Authority in 365 districts at the National Level where adult female literacy was below 50% with a special focus on the education of rural illiterate women in the age group of 15 and above with preference to SC, ST, Minority (Muslims) and disadvantaged backward People.¹⁸

All these programmes and Schemes of the Government of India aim at making women independent and self reliant. Despite the enactment of a lot of social legislations, the welfare schemes for women lagged behind men in different spheres. In order to improve the women's social status in the society, Tamil Nadu government is implementing various welfare programmes for the overall development of women.

Women Education in Present Scenario

In 1951, the female literacy was only 8.9 per cent. It has increased to 39.3 per cent in 1991 and according to the 53rd round of National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO), the literacy rate of female now stands at 50 per cent as compared to 73 per cent in male literacy at the end of December 1997.¹⁹ The literacy rate of Women has increased from 8.9 % in 1951 to 65.5% in 2011.As per the report (2021), India’s country-wide female literacy rate is 70.3%,while the male literacy rate is estimated at 84.7%.India’s average literacy rate stands at 77.7%(!9 May-2023), according to the National Statistical Office (NSO).²⁰ As shown in below Table, there has been a considerable increase in the rate of literacy of female in last two decades.

Female Literacy Status 1951-2021

Year	Total Literacy (inmillion)	Rate of Literacy (Male)	Rate of Literacy (Female)	Total	Male Female Difference
1951	60.1	27.2	8.9	16.7	18.3
1961	105.5	40.4	15.4	24.0	25.0
1971	161.5	46.6	22.0	29.5	24.0
1981	241.0	56.4	29.8	36.2	27.4
1991	362.2	63.1	39.3	43.3	23.8
2001	666.94	75.3	53.6	64.84	21.7
2011	778.45	82.1	65.5	74.4	16.6
2021	867.34	84.7	70.3	77.7	14.4

Sources: Census of India (2011) and <https://www.findeasy.in>

It was noticed that during 1951-2021, the rate of female literacy has been increased by seven times.Again it was observed that since 1981,the male-female difference is getting closer which is a positive indication on the part of the education of women in our country. However ,it is noticed that the rate of female literacy is 65.5% as against the male literacy is of 82.1%.This shows that still the percent of literacy among female is 16.6% less than that of male. However, the increase in female education is not enough. The percentage of female education is less as compared to male.²¹ Hence, it is imperative to take a special intervention for enhancing the education of female in our

country even today. The most important reason for this is the lack of female education due to the problems faced by women in the society and in the family.²² This can be found in the following headings,

Problems of Women Education in India

Our Traditional Thinking

The most important hurdle in the way of the women education is our traditional thinking. It is said that in our society girls are confined to the house holding activities. There is no need for them to be educated. Instead educating sons is more beneficial than educating the daughters. Hence anti- woman attitude prevailing in the society is a barrier in education of the girls or women.

Economic Status of the Family

The economic condition of most of the families is not good in India. Poverty and unemployment are major problems. It is supposed that women are made to hold the family responsibilities. In poor states, the percentage of women education is less than the richer states. In Haryana, Punjab, Mizoram, Chandigarh, Kerala, the status of women education is better than Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan. Hence economic problems also serve as a barrier in educating the girl child.

Feeling of Social Insecurity

It is said that the security of the girls before the marriage is done by father, in young age it is carried out by her husband and in old age it is done by her son. Women are supposed to be insecure in the society even today because of the same reasons her parents want her to be married as early as possible and in doing so her education is neglected. Without security it will not be possible to achieve the objective of education for the equality of the women.

Lack of Finance

However many educational institutes have been opened for the women yet there are many under construction. Finance plays a big role in this way. If proper and adequate

finance is given by government and it is properly utilized then a number of good educational institutes can be opened.

Early Marriages

In our society, girls are supposed to be burden for the family. After girl's maturity, parents have anxiety for the marriage of the girl child. Therefore they are getting married in an early age. Because of the early marriage they suffer many problems in their life.

Illiteracy of the Parents

Through national literacy mission many illiterates are being made literate through even then many adults are still illiterate. They do not understand the importance of the education. They are not conscious about the education of their daughters hence illiteracy of the parents is a major problem in education of the girl child. Apart from this, in a patriarchal society, parents do not give their daughters the importance they give to their sons, and most of their daughters at the cost of educating them, which is the biggest obstacle to female education.

Lack of Special Institutions for Girls:

In India most of the educational institutes are co educational. There are a few educational institutes made only for the girls. Parents worry about the girl's security in sending in these educational institutions that's why the education of the girls is facing stagnation. For security basis separate educational institutes should be opened.

Distance of the Educational Institutions from the Home:

Distance of the educational institutions from the home area affects the attendance and registration . In India girls go to educational institutions in a very limited number due to the location of institutions at distant places. Afterwards they leave their studies. That's why they are deprived of education.

Problem of Co- education:

Parents have anxiety about the safety of their girl child. The Co - educational institutes are not considered as safe . Moreover seeing in the news, now a day's many rape cases are noticed . In such cases reliability in these institutions become less. That's why parents hamper the education of their girl child.

Scarcity of the Lady Teachers :

The appointed male teachers in educational institutions are not trusted by the parents of the girl child . They want that there should be appointment of female teachers for imparting education to their girl child so that their safety can be assured . Studies have shown that male teachers are appointed more than female teachers despite of reservation in the sheets for women in jobs . Therefore women teachers should be maximized for training and educating the girl child

Lack of Enthusiasm and Interest of the Officials in-charge of the Education :

Officers don't take interest in spreading awareness about the education . They don't fulfil their responsibility in an appropriate manner . Corruption is prevailing in education system too . Lack of interest and enthusiasm also a great hindrance in the path of educating a girl child . Some important suggestions and recommendations to improve female literacy rate in India are given below

Suggestion and Recommendation:

1. To have more girls ' schools in rural and urban areas. Appointment of qualified teachers, preferably more female teachers in government schools
2. To design relevant curriculum to achieve better status in society. Making schools more accessible by increasing their number or ensuring safer ways of commuting.
3. To provide compulsory free education for girls up to secondary school and to provide books and study materials free of cost for poor and needy girls.
4. To enable women to adopt modern techniques for household activities so as to free them for education and other social activities.
5. To implement suitable extension programmes to change the attitude of society towards women's liberation.

Towards enhancing the educational opportunities and providing better social status for women, the following special efforts could be taken:

1. To open more women's colleges wherever necessary and to offer a variety of courses in Humanities and Sciences.

2. To introduce women's studies in the curriculum of higher education so that both men and women can study and analyse the current issues and problems relating to women and arrive at remedial measures to bring in possible changes in society.
3. To provide more opportunities for women to participate in academic and applied research activities on par with men.
4. To offer more employment facilities for women who have received higher education. It helps not only improve their living standards but also motivate many others to opt for higher education.

Conclusion

Women education is the ladder of the success and development of every individual and Nation. It is necessary to provide girls and women with proper resources so that they can get educated. Female education played an important role in the societal growth as well as its economic development. Education is considered as a Key instrument for the women empowerment. Therefore, It is not enough if the government pays attention to the promotion of female education, If every member of the family encourages the male members of their family to learn education, If they give equal importance to the male to improve the education of their family, there is no doubt that not only the family but also our country will become better.

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